

Examining the Impact of cooperative learning strategies on student performance in geography, Nine years basic Education Program, GS Musherri, Musherri Sector

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Abstract

The study concerns the impact of cooperative learning on students performance in geography in nine years basic education of Musherri Sector. The study used descriptive survey design, 46 subjects was used as sample size from 230 as target population. Stratified sampling and purpose sampling were used to get sample size, questionnaire and interview guide were used to collect data and Microsoft excel has been used to analyze data. The study found that teachers use different cooperative learning methods including jigsaw, think pair share, three minute review , team work and group performance.

The study found that 17.4% of the respondents revealed that teachers use round tables tables as the the simple cooperative learning structure that is used in the G.S Musherri which has enabled them to cover much content that has enabled to build team spirit and incorporates writing.

Out of 46 respondents 36.9% indicated that teacher's negative attitude was a reason leading to lack of effective use of corporative learning in the classroom. This was brought up by the issue of lack of teachers' motivation. The study recommend to have assessment as daily competition , quizzes, tests and any other type of assessment to increase student performance.

The study recommended the government to train teachers on skills of cooperative learning as one way of helping students to learn and also to have continous professional development to teachers on methods of teaching and learning.

Key words: cooperative learning, student performance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Cooperative learning is a pedagogical practice that has attracted much attention over the last three decades because of a large body of research that indicates students gain both academically and socially when they have opportunities to interact with others to accomplish shared goals (Johnson 2012; Lou et al. 1996; Slavin, 1996). Through interaction students learn to interrogate issues, share ideas, clarify differences, and construct new understandings (Mercer, Wegerif & Dawes, 1999; Webb & Mastergeorge, 2003).

Education is the passage of knowledge from persons with knowhow to the persons with a desire to get enlightened (Robyn, 2014). This could be accomplished through cooperative learning. According to research, college students perform better through cooperative learning than from a teacher-centered approach (Robyn). This is due to the ability to integrate interpersonal relationships to social interdependence theory (You, 2014). Cooperative learning also enables students to effectively accomplish practical procedures, perform valid research hence making it easier for the educators to manage student's learning. In addition, CL encourages the students to effectively contribute towards the problems solving leading to better understanding of the subjects (Davidson & Major, 2014). Hence, cooperative learning could be presumed to be a better approach that could benefit students in Saudi Arabia, only if it could be implemented properly. Traditional learning is a teacher-centered method that focuses on memorization and rote learning. In Saudi Arabia, traditional learning is the commonly adopted strategy in college education. However, according to research cooperative learning may benefit students more than the traditional approach (Mohammad, 2004). According to research, students' participative and active involvement in subjects increase their level of understanding (You, 2014). Through making learning fun, enjoyable and autonomous, cooperative learning could be effective in enhancing the understanding of students (You, 2014).

In every aspect of life, effective learning requires teamwork and cooperation to enhance the productivity of individuals. Learning institutions also operate the same way (Dallmer, 2007). For example, adopting cooperative learning would enable the students to learn from each other; this enables them to immensely gain interpersonal skills through group participation (Davidson &

Major, 2014). Furthermore, cooperative learning enables the students to have broader understanding of the subjects since they are able to collaborate in the learning process. This affirms that students who adopt jigsaw strategy are able to perform better academically compared with their counterparts who are taught through teacher-centered strategy (Robyn, 2014). In cooperative learning, group discussions enhance higher understanding comparatively to traditional or conventional teaching that heavily depends on teachers as resources. This implies that academic excellence is based on team work (You, 2014). Hence cooperative learning could be classified among ways of embracing teamwork in academics. Many college students would be willing to learn, share skills and competencies with their colleagues, and also develop leadership and other important aspects of teamwork (Davidson & Major, 2014)..

Cooperative learning has begun to show potential benefits in the Rwandan education system in many aspects. For example, it increases student's understanding of content, academic achievements, and participation in class. Hence, cooperative learning condition has enabled students to be challenged by their colleagues; this triggers the desire and agility to spend extra time to digest learning contents that are not well understood. In fact, the students get to learn from their colleagues through consultations in cooperative learning environment.

1.2. Purpose of the study.

The study examine the impact of cooperative learning on students' performance in geography in G.S Musheru, Nyagatare District.

1.3. Objectives of the study

1. To find out methods of cooperative learning used in geography in G.S Musheru.
2. To identify the effects of the cooperative learning on the students' performance in the geography.
3. To identify the challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning in G.S Musheru.

2. Review of related literature

Slavin (1983), asserted that learning is a step-by-step process in which an individual experiences permanent, lasting changes in knowledge, behaviors, or ways of processing the world. Let's go through a few examples of different types of learning you might hear about in the field of educational psychology.

Cooperative learning is a learning process that involves restructuring classes within small groups so that teamwork is embraced. In addition, it is a learning strategy that encourages group participation in handling assignments and academic or learning problems (Dallmer, 2007). Cooperative learning is a teaching approach in which small groups, each with learners of diverse levels of capability, use a range of educational activities to enhance their comprehension of a topic (Dyson & Casey, 2012). Cooperative education is one of the recent remarkable and productive areas of research, theory, and practice in learning. It denotes students functioning together to attain the objectives and the instructional events that organize the students' joint efforts (Gömleksiz, 2007).

Teachers used different methods in teaching and learning process that include: student team learning, jigsaw, group investigations and learning together. the student team learning method was developed by Slavin (1983 a). the two most popular student team learning methods are student teams-achievement divisions) and teams-games-tournaments). in both the methods, students are grouped in teams and they compete against each other. Student teams consist of students with different achievement levels. teams' overall grade is based on the collective improvement of the team members. Teams game -tournament consist of games and tournaments in which teams are formed with the students of same achievement level.

The jigsaw method was developed by Aaronson (1978) and is based on the concept of division of labour among the individual group members. here each student is responsible for completing a task and teaching the task to the rest of the group. an intermediate step in jigsaw method would be such that a student of one group discusses and compare the results with the students from other groups.

The group investigations method was developed by sharan & sharan (1976). this method is similar to the jigsaw method. in this method, each group has a different task and groups create

presentations to teach the rest of the class. This method is unique because of the use of open-ended problems that provide students a significant control on the subtasks. students are assessed on their presentations. Learning together was developed by Johnson (1975). learning together is based on the belief that all students work together on the same task and should share a common goal. Johnson and Johnson offered five characteristics of cooperative learning (1994 b).

In the era what we call information society, one of the most important skills is cooperation. In early days, studying with someone else was defined as an indicator of dependency, but today learning together and asking for help is considered among the best strategies for learning to learn (Chen, 2002). Producing information, theorizing or developing models in a field requires more complicated information and skills. Therefore, common mind is better than the single best mind. The common mind is more effective for the mentioned novelties or, in other words, in creating acceptable change in society. All the systems from health to economics, law to education, information industry to the service industry consider cooperative working among priorities in order to keep up with the times and make a difference in the society. The output of the education system provides the labor force input for other systems. For this reason, the efficiency and productivity of the education system is proportional to its ability to raise the desired labor force for other systems. Under these circumstances, cooperative working habit should be brought in to students at all levels of education systems (Slavin, 1987; Johnson & Johnson, 1999).

According to Johnson (2009) cooperative learning is more than just asking students to sit and work together. Research has identified some components that mediate the effectiveness of cooperative learning, such as: (a) positive interdependence, which allows students to perceive that they are linked with each other in such a way that one cannot succeed unless everyone succeeds, (b) individual accountability, which gives each member of the group a sense of personal responsibility toward goal achievement, (c) promotive interaction, which takes place when students facilitate each other's efforts to learn through exchanging resources, help, motivation, and points of view, (d) interpersonal and smallgroup skills, which means that students must be taught social skills for high quality cooperation, and (e) group processing, which exists when group members discuss how well they are achieving their goals and maintaining their working relationships (Johnson & Johnson, 2009).

Cooperative learning cannot be taught through verbal instruction. Students can adopt cooperative learning through a process that involves working together in groups, developing a product at the end and examining both the product and cooperative learning skills. "Cooperative learning" (CL) method emerges in the literature as a method that assists instructors in carrying out this process. CL emerges when students gather in order to reach a common goal (Johnson & Johnson, 1999). Each member of the group reaches his goal only if all the other members reach their own learning goals (Deutsch, 1962). Acikgoz (2002) defines cooperative learning as working of students in small groups and helping each other in the learning process. There are certain principles and requirements for the implementation of CL. These are;

- Positive Interdependence: Each individual depends on the other members of the group. Each individual complements others.
- Individual Accountability: Individual accountability is the evaluation of each individual's performance and effect of the result on individual and group success.
- Face to face interaction: Group members reach success by helping each other and sharing ideas. As face to face interaction increases in this process, the sense of responsibility and social solidarity increases.
- Social Skills: As the students are in a group in the cooperative learning, they acquire social skills better.
- Evaluation of the Group Processing: At the end of the group work, students gather and discuss the productivity of the project and whether they have reached the goals (Johnson & Johnson, 1999; Johnson, Johnson & Smith, 1998).

Based on Bandura's Social Dependency Theory, Behavioral Learning Theory (Johnson, Johnson & Smith, 1998) and Vygotsky's (1978) "Zone of Proximal Development" theory. Social Dependency Theory assumes that the way to form social dependency is about how social dependency develops, how individual interacts and what the result will be as a result of the interaction. Accordingly, positive interdependence (cooperative approach) results in such an interaction that the group members encourage, support and improve the efforts of the individuals. Behavioral Learning Theory focuses on the effect of group consolidation and rewards on learning. According to this theory, behaviors, which are rewarded externally, are repeated. While, Skinner (1985), one of the representatives of behavioral cult, focuses on the group coincidences, Bandura

focuses on the imitation. Slavin (1987) has recently stated that external "group awards" are needed in order to motivate the individuals to learn in groups based on cooperative learning (Saban, 2005).

According to the Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development Theory, a student can take his/her learning to the optimum level by asking for help when he/she is stuck. The person to whom he asks for help may be his/her teacher or friend. It has been found out that CL has important effects on improving academic success of students (Hall, 1988; Tarim, 2003; Kolawole, 2007; Gok. Dogan, Doymus & Karacop, 2009; Ahmad & Mahmood, 2010, Capar, 2011; Parveen & Batool, 2012), developing desirable attitudes toward courses (Yavuz, 2007), providing motivation (Nichols & Miller, 1994; Margolis & McCabe, 2003; Salili & Lai, 2003; Kus, Filiz & Altun, 2014; Yoshida, Tani, Uchida, Masui & Nakayama, 2014;), adopting cooperative working habit (Rienties, Tempelaar, Bossche, Gijsselaers & Segers, 2009), and improving favorable competition skills (Kong, Kwok & Fang, 2012) in studies from different fields.

Although there are many techniques in CL, Jigsaw and Team Game Tournament (TGT) techniques were used in this study. Jigsaw technique was developed by Aronson (2000). Students are divided into groups of 5-6 members in this technique. Each member works on his subject and students from different groups working on the same subject gather and create expert groups. The subject is discussed in depth in the expert groups. Students learn the subject completely in the expert groups and teach their subject to other students when they return to their original groups. Even if the students are graded individually, students need others for a good mark and therefore this technique requires cooperative working (Slavin, 1987; Arends, 1998; Aronson, 2000; Senemoglu, 2012). TGT technique was developed by Slavin and Oickle (1981). After the teacher or students make the presentation related to the courses, students are divided into heterogeneous groups in this technique. After the students teach the subject to each other, students compete with the students at the same level from other groups at the tournament table. The team points are calculated by summing the points of students. The groups with high points are rewarded (Slavin, 1995; Arends, 1998). It is stated that individuals have benefited from Science and Technology instruction in using these scientific process and principles for decision-making and in participating in scientific discussions affecting the society and developing their skills to producing ideas on a subject (Akcaay & Yager, 2010).

According to another approach, the use of ICT and other Science and Technology instruction is an easy and tangible instruction that should be conducted with proper method and techniques by taking the interests, needs, level of development, desires and environmental facilities of students (Hancer, Sensoy & Yildirim, 2003). As can be understood from the explanations, for an effective Science and Technology instruction, students' sense of curiosity should be enhanced and an active environment in which students can discover and produce information should be created. The complicated structure of the Science and Technology course requires cooperation for students to learn the subjects (Yagci, Kaptı & Beyaztas, 2012). Moreover, implementation of cooperative learning method in Geography classes is advised by the Ministry of National Education (Ministry of National Education, 2005).

Many research literatures indicate the efficacy of cooperative learning for student learning and development ("Cooperative Learning", n.d.). Teachers feel professional pressure to use this research-based teaching strategy and try to implement cooperative learning without adequate training ("Cooperative Learning", n.d.). This results in giving "group activities" to students, which is labeled as cooperative learning. These students, teachers, and administrators then grow dissatisfied with the results of their "cooperative learning" experience. These individuals are often "inoculated" against cooperative learning on the basis of their exposure to group work ("Cooperative Learning", n.d.).

Sheehy found that though she had experienced successful cooperative learning, fellow teachers using cooperative learning experienced some difficulties in the classroom. Sheehy noticed that though students have been tested, observed, videotaped, and analyzed; their voices seemed missing in the literatures. Sheehy found that it is important to understand students' social, emotional and mathematical experiences of cooperative problem solving team from students' perspectives. In Sheehy's dissertation (Sheehy, 2004, p. 174).

Johnson and Johnson stated that teachers must assess the contribution of individual members to the group's work in order to ensure that each individual is accountable for doing their job in the group's work (Sheehy, 2004). Sheehy observed that regardless of however meaningful this contribution, students feel pressured to contribute an idea or the completion of a task to their group's activity. Sheehy noticed that the assessment of individual accountability indicates that

mathematical activity supporting the group is valued more than activity enhancing individual learning.

“The purpose of group processing is to clarify and improve the effectiveness of the members in contributing to the efforts to achieve the group’s goals” (Sheehy, 2004, p.183). For group processing to be effective, teachers should provide students with organized format for discussion. Group processing promotes behavior that promotes the group goal rather than behavior that promotes mathematics. If the group goal was to solve a specific problem, then group processing would center on questions like: What did each group member contribute to finding this formula? How could your group work together tomorrow to solve problems more effectively? What is one thing each individual could improve on? If individual mathematical activity was privileged in group processing, questions would center on questions like: What was the first idea each participant had? How many different representations/ideas were discussed? How were the ideas connected? How did the group agree upon one representation? Why? How would each member proceed with or extend the problem?

Teachers and students generally interpret social interaction as a required characteristic of effective learning in cooperative groups. A student who does not engage in conversation is often referred to as a “free-rider” or antisocial or is accused of not supporting and contributing to the group. The expectation of interaction might create a social pressure on group members to share their own ideas and suggestions as well as listen to those of others. Hence self/other binary tension emerges when individuals believe that their individual mathematical activity is valued only when it is shared and possibly only when the group takes it up. Because students do not feel free to reflect quietly on their own mathematics or to dismiss the ideas of others without polite consideration, the expectation of interaction could significantly hinder mathematical activity of the individual learner (Sheehy, 2004).

Johnson said that teachers must not only hold individuals accountable for what they contribute to their group, but also for how they contribute and interact with other group members. Sheehy found that although the ability to work with other people is an important characteristic to develop with students, the self/other binary tensions this structure creates not only leads to a decreased focus on individual learning but also on mathematics altogether. The findings of Sheehy’s study reveal that if a student perceives manners rather than mathematics as privileged in a cooperative learning

environment, the student tends to do what is socially expected rather than what furthers student's own mathematics. This privileging leads to a number of problematic outcomes; such as, students abandoning their own ideas in order to be respectful of others, forfeiting their own reflection time in order to actively participate in group activity, or accepting one solution instead of many in order to arrive at one agreed on group solution.

3.METHODOLOGY

The researcher used descriptive survey study design, both qualitative and quantitative approach were used to get data. The study used stratified sample size and purposive sampling to get sample size of 46 respondents that including 20 teachers, 15 students, 10 parents and 1 Sector education officer. Questionnaire and interview guide were used to collect data, reliability and validity has been done to ensure validity of the content. Data analysis was done using Microsoft word.

4. FINDINGS, DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

4.1.1 Gender of respondents.

Data relating to respondents' gender of respondent was collected to determine whether males and females participated.

Table 1: showing the gender of respondents.

Gender	No. of Respts	Percentage
Male	29	63.0%
Female	17	37.0%
Total	46	100

Source: Primary Data, 2017

Figure 2: showing the gender of respondents.

The findings in Table 3 show that most of the respondents (63.0%) were males while only (37.0%) of them were females. This scenario is associated with the fact that, in the area where this study was conducted, female teachers in the secondary section is still low and this was clearly translating in their enrolment at secondary level. However the ratio of the female and male students was almost the same. The gender of the respondents was further presented in the figure 1 below.

4.2 Age bracket of respondents .

Data relating to respondents' age group was collected to determine which age group participated most. Respondents' age demographics helped the researcher to find out the age bracket of staff , students , parents and education officer of Musheru sector .

Table 2: Showing the age bracket of respondents.

Age Bracket	No. of Respts	Percentage
13-25 yrs	17	37.0
26-32 yrs	9	19.6
33-40	11	23.9
41-49	5	10.9
50-56	3	6.5
57+	1	2.2
Total	46	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2017

From Table 2, it can also be noted that majority of the respondents (37.0%) were aged between 13-25 years and these were mainly students and few new teachers who have just entered the teaching profession. About 19.6% and 23.9% were aged between 26-32 years and 33-40 years above years respectively. The majority of the teachers and administrators were within the age bracket of 26 – 40 scored the highest percentage of all, that means they still strong and energetic to fill teaching profession. The factor that the researcher had respondents represented from both the young and old age meant she obtained unbiased data. The information on the age of the respondents were further represented in the figure 2 below.

Figure 1: showing the age of the respondents.

4.1.3 Marital status of respondents .

Data relating to respondents' marital status group was collected to determine which marital group participated most. Respondents' marital status demographics helped the researcher to find out the marital status bracket of staff , students , parents and education officer of Musheru sector .

Table 3: The marital status of respondents.

TEACHERS AND ADMINISTRATORS		
Marital status	No. of Respts	Percentage
Single	3	18.8
Married	11	68.8
Divorced	1	6.3
Widowed	1	6.3
Widower	0	0.0
Total	16	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2017

According to the table, 68.8% are married, 18.8% are single, 6.3% are divorced and 0% is widowed. This indicates that the respondents are stable at their work since the highest percentages are for married people.

Figure 4: The marital status of respondents.

4.1.4: Qualification of respondents.

The research was also carried out to determine whether respondents were in position to provide informed responses on the subject under study.

Table 4. Qualification of respondents

TEACHERS AND ADMINISTRATORS		
Marital status	No. of Respts	Percentage
Certificate	03	18.75%
Diploma	04	25.0%
Degree	09	56.25%
Total	16	100

Source; Primary Data.

The findings revealed that 18.75% of the respondents were certificate holders, 25% were diploma holders and 56.25% were degree holders. It is also observed that the majority of the teachers were professionals who had attained the either certificate , diploma or degree in education . According

to the findings, most of the teachers and administrators of G.S Musherri were degree holders who are competent and were rightly qualified .

Figure4. Qualification of respondents

4.2 Respondents’ opinion on methods of cooperative learning used.

Several items in the questionnaire were presented to the respondents to rate the methods of cooperative learning used by G.S Musherri.

The respondents were asked to reveal whether there are various methods of cooperative learning used during teaching and learning process. Their responses were presented in the table below.

Table 5: Showing whether there are cooperative methods used in teaching.

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	46	100%
No	0	0%
Total	46	100

Source: Primary Data, 2017

Figure6: Showing whether there are cooperative methods used in teaching.

All respondents agreed that they incorporate cooperative learning in the class rooms to ensure students contribute ideas or to complete task to their activity to ensure individual learning through the support of the group members. This implies that the teachers and students of G.S Musherri incorporate collaborative learning during teaching and learning process .

Through the interview guide with one of the students in the G.S Musherri , she asserted that her geography teacher use the groups during assigning the assessments to students , this has allowed them to grasp the content and solving the problems easily since it is done in the groups.

Also respondents were requested to reveal to the different methods of cooperative learning that ae used by teachers in the G.S Musherri. The information obtained from the respondents were presented in the table below.

Table 7: Methods of cooperative learning that are used by teachers in G.S Musherri.

Methods of cooperative learning used	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Round table	8	17.4
Jigsaw technique	6	13.0
Think-Pair-Share	11	23.9
Three-minute review	4	8.7
Teamwork	10	21.7
Group performance	7	15.2
Total	46	100

Source: Primary Data, 2017.

Figure8: Methods of cooperative learning that are used by teachers in G.S Musherri.

From the study findings , 17.4% of the respondents revealed that they use round tables as represented by . Through the interview guide that was conducted with one of the teachers in the primary section she asserted that “round tables have been the simple cooperative learning structures that is used in the G.S Musherri which has enabled them to cover much content that has enabled to build team spirit and incorporates writing. She also revealed to the researcher round tables this

provides struggling learners access to additional reinforcement, while high achievers may pursue enrichment activities like independent research. Ability grouping is appropriate during participation science lesson or after assessments, when there are apparent gaps in learners understanding”.

Also from the research findings 6 respondents who represent 13.0% of the total respondents revealed that they use jigsaw technique. One of the secondary teacher revealed that “within jigsaw technique the class he divides students into team , where each team member is responsible for learning a specific part of a topic. After meeting with members of other groups , who are the “experts” in the same part , the “learners” return to their on groups and presents their finings. This has enabled learners to understand the content easily”.

23.9% of the respondents revealed to the researcher that they use think pair share method. One of teachers revealed that he use think pair share method to allow students to contemplate a posed question or problem silently. He said that “student writes down thoughts or simply just brainstorm in his or her head. When prompted, the student pairs up with a peer and discusses his or her idea(s) and then listens to the ideas of his or her partner. Following pair dialogue, the teacher solicits responses from the whole group. When teachers use this technique they don't have to worry about students not volunteering because each student will already have an idea in their heads, therefore, the teacher can call on anyone and increase discussion productivity”.

Other respondents 8.7% of the respondents said that they use three minute review. From the interview guide conducted with the students they said “the teachers give them three or more minutes to review the previous work. The continued and said that this has given them chance to grasp the content easily”.

The other group of the respondents said that they use team work technique 21.7%, One of the teachers in secondary section revealed to the research that “team work during teaching and learning of geography has enabled individual The success of the team can only be truly attained if individual responsibility leads all the members to fulfill their duties. Within such procedures we can distinguish four methods: He also asserted that the classroom organization with this method

allowed us to create an intergroup procedure so as to compare the degree of performance of the different teams. It consists of creating teams of 4 to 5 students and arrange a competition with the members of the other teams. There is also evaluation with the awarding of marks”.

15.2% of other respondents asserted that they use group performance . This method has enabled the competition in the class since the students aim at scoring many marks promotes intrinsic motivation, with the commitment to the chosen subtopic and the work plan of the team members and autonomy and has also resulted into high level of grasping of the content.

The above methods of cooperative learning were further represented in the figure below for clear understanding.

4.3 Effects of cooperative learning on students performance.

The respondents were tasked to reveal to the researcher whether there are effects of cooperative learning on students performance . The table below shows the response of the sampled respondents on the appropriateness of cooperative learning on students.

Table 9: showing the response on the effects of cooperative learning.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	37	80.4
No	3	6.5
I don't know	6	13.0
Total	46	8.7

Source: Primary Data, (September 2017)

Figure10: showing the response on the effects of cooperative learning.

From the study finding the majority of the respondents 80.4% said that there are various effects of the cooperative learning on the students performance, 13.0% said that they do not know and these were mainly the learners while 6.5% of other respondents said that they do not involve cooperative learning in teaching and learning process and this was mainly attributed by the conservativeness of the teachers on traditional methods.

The respondents were also tasked to reveal the effects of cooperative learning, the responses obtained from the field were presented in the table below.

Table 11: Showing the effects of cooperative learning.

Effects of cooperative learning	Frequency	Percentage
Cooperative learning involves active learning	07	15.2
Depending on the activities, it is possible to divide out components and share workload	19	41.3
Depending on the activities, it is possible to divide out components and share workload	05	10.9

Working successful in groups assists in development of transferable skills	15	32.6
Total	46	100

Source: Primary Data, 2017.

Figure 12: Showing the effects of cooperative learning.

Out of 46 respondents, 15.2% indicated that cooperative learning involves active learning by encouraging sharing of ideas that avoid boredom. The finding were further supported by the finding presented by Jane Jane (2010), when learners get actively involved in the materials deeper learning and understanding usually results. Further 19 out of 46 (41.3%) respondents indicated that Learners feel less isolated and alone. Learners feel less isolated especially at the beginning of the activity in participation, they have support at the where to start stage Esther (2009). The results in table above shows that 5 out of 46 (10.9%) respondents indicate that depending on the activities, components are divided and workloads shared Kimaku (2001). The activity is done much faster and become easier. Less time is used in a certain activity and the learner manages to handle different tasks within a short time Edward (2008). The research shows that a group of 15 (32.6%) of the respondents indicated that working successfully in groups assists in development of transferable skills Emily (2009).

4.4 The challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning in G.S Musheru.

The respondents were also tasked to reveal whether there are various challenges faced while implementing cooperative learning in G.S Musheru. Table below further elaborates on the reasons for ineffective use of cooperative learning in G.S Musheru on participation in science classrooms. The main objective of the study was to find out the reasons why cooperative learning in G.S Musheru is not effectively used. This was brought up by the issue of learners not achieving the goal at the end of participation in geography. The findings on whether there are various challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning in G.S Musheru were presented in the table below.

Table 13: Showing whether there are various challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning.

Response		Frequency	Percentage
Yes		46	100
No		00	00
Total		46	100

Source: Primary Data (September 2017)

Figure8: Showing the effects of cooperative learning.

According to the research findings as presented in the table 6 above shows that the majority said that there are various challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning .

The respondents were also tasked to reveal the challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning, the responses on the challenges facing cooperative learning were presented in the table 7 below.

Table 14: Showing challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning

challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning	Frequency	Percentage
Large number of learners per class	11	23.9
Lack of enough compound for the centres	8	17.4
Lack of learners confidence	03	10.9
Language barrier	02	4.3
Teacher's negative attitude	17	36.9

Lack of professional skills	05	10.9
Total	46	100

Source: Primary Data, 2017.

Figure 15: Showing challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning

Lack of enough field for the centres was a reason stated by 8 (17.4%) of the respondents. The compound set aside for centres are very small compared to the number of learners enrolled per class annually. Even in the schools that have enough compounds do not have trees that provide learners with shades. Yet the school compounds help to provide favourable learning area for learners in groups.

Out of 46 respondents, 10.9% indicated that lack of learners confidence was a reasons leading to lack of effective use of cooperative learning during teaching and learning process. Some of the learners are shy and fearful while using cooperative learning alone during participation which in turn leads to intimidation by others learners. Some of the learners comes from rich families and are not taught how to handle things by their own they always rely on their house helps.

Language barrier was a reason indicated by 4.3% of the respondents. Teachers use English and French while explaining during participation in the study area due to the fact the some learners are pure Rwandans who have poor background on the use of English since at home are brought up from families that use Kinyarwanda as medium of communication yet in the schools English and some times French are used as the medium of instruction and the majority do not understand well . Teachers find it difficult to communicate to those who are not yet fluent in English. According to the interview conducted with one the students , he asserted that it is difficult for him to communicate to the fellows in English, yet it is English that is allowed to be used while discussing with the fellow classmates during teaching and learning process.

Out of 46 respondents 36.9% indicated that teacher's negative attitude was a reason leading to lack of effective use of corporative learning in the classroom. This was brought up by the issue of lack of teachers' motivation. Some teachers have negative attitude on the use groups in classrooms as most of them think that students can not afford to discuss in the groups yet students are already experts in the use of groups.

Out of 46 respondents, 23.9% indicated that the reasons for not using the Coorporative learning effectively was the large number of learners per class. The GSM consist of learners was near by nine year basic education schools with the poor background therefore teacher need to concentrate on each to ensure that the desired concept is glued into the mind. This means that if the number of learners is large, the teacher lack sufficient time to explain to each on how to use the groups. The large number of learners resulted from the introduction of free 12 year basic education.

Out of 46 respondents, 10.9% reavealed that some teachers lack of professional skills to enable them use cooperative learning.Lack of these skills deny any teacher the knowledge required in imparting learners on how to use cooperative learning.

5.CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENATIONS

The study found out that 17.4% of the respondents revealed that they use round tables. Round tables have been the simple cooperative learning structure that is used in the G.S Musheru which has enabled them to cover much content that has enabled to build team spirit and incorporates writing.

The study also found out that 13.0% of the respondents supported the use of jigsaw technique in G.S Musheru as the cooperative learning method. Teachers divide students into teams, where from each team member is responsible for learning specific part of a topic.

Each student gets a part of the necessary information to do the task, becoming “expert” in his/her jigsaw piece or knowledge part. The team members are responsible for knowing the corresponding information in depth, for teaching it and for learning the information presented by the rest of the team member.

The research findings also stated that the teachers use think pair to allow students to contemplate a posed question or problem silently. In think pair method student writes down thoughts or simply just brainstorm in his or her head. When prompted, the student pairs up with a peer and discusses his or her idea(s) and then listens to the ideas of his or her partner. Following pair dialogue, the teacher solicits responses from the whole group. When teachers use this technique they don't have to worry about students not volunteering because each student will already have an idea in their heads, therefore, the teacher can call on anyone and increase discussion productivity. This is inline with the findings presented by Johnson,(1999) In heterogeneous teams of 4 or 5 members, the students cooperate to obtain a product in group. The reward is based on the mean of the team which is established from individual progress.

The study sought to establish the effects of cooperative learning on students performance. It was apparent that the 15.2% indicated that cooperative learning involves active learning by encouraging sharing of ideas that avoid boredom. The finding were further supported by the finding presented by Jane Jane (2010), when learners get actively involved in the materials deeper learning and understanding usually results. Further 19 out of 46 (41.3%) respondents indicated that Learners feel less isolated and alone. Learners feel less isolated especially at the beginning of the activity in participation, they have support at the where to start stage Esther (2009). The results in

table above shows that 5 out of 46 (10.9%) respondents indicate that depending on the activities, components are divided and workloads shared Kimaku (2001). The activity is done much faster and become easier. Less time is used in a certain activity and the learner manages to handle different tasks within a short time Edward (2008). The research shows that a group of 15 (32.6%) of the respondents indicated that working successfully in groups assists in development of transferable skills Emily (2009).

The study sought to establish the challenges faced in the implementation of cooperative learning in G.S Musheru. The study finding found out that 10.9% indicated that lack of learners confidence was a reasons leading to lack of effective use of cooperative learning during teaching and learning process. Some of the learners are shy and fearful while using cooperative learning alone during participation which in turn leads to intimidation by others learners. Some of the learners comes from rich families and are not taught how to handle things by their own they always rely on their house helps.

Language barrier was a reason indicated by 4.3% of the respondents. Teachers use English and French while explaining during participation in the study area due to the usage of Kinyarwanda at home and learners weak on the use of English as their families use Kinyarwanda as communication. Sometimes of the teachers use English and French as the medium of instruction and the majority do not understand well. Teachers find it difficult to communicate to those who are not yet fluent in English. According to the interview conducted with one the students, he asserted that it is difficult for him to communicate to the fellows in English, yet it is English that is allowed to be used while discussing with the fellow classmates during teaching and learning process.

Out of 46 respondents 36.9% indicated that teacher's negative attitude was a reason leading to lack of effective use of corporative learning in the classroom. This was brought up by the issue of lack of teachers' motivation. Some teachers have negative attitude on the use groups in classrooms as most of them think that students can not afford to discuss in the groups yet students are already experts in the use of groups.

Out of 46 respondents, 23.9% indicated that the reasons for not using the Coorporative learning effectively was the large number of learners per class. The GSM consist of learners was near by

nine year basic education schools with the poor background therefore teacher need to concentrate on each to ensure that the desired concept is glued into the mind. This means that if the number of learners is large, the teacher lack sufficient time to explain to each on how to use the groups. The large number of learners resulted from the introduction of free 12 year basic education.

Out of 46 respondents, 10.9% revealed that some teachers lack of professional skills to enable them use cooperative learning. Lack of these skills deny any teacher the knowledge required in imparting learners on how to use cooperative learning.

Conclusion.

Following the results of the study it can concluded that grouping learners is very important. This was evident as the respondents indicated that they knew importance of grouping in different ways. The grouping has benefited the learners to some extent of development of transferable skills as indicated by some of the respondents. Finally the study concluded that management of cooperative learning has effects in the improvement of pupils' participation in classroom. This was evident as the respondents indicated that records help teachers to be conversant with feeble areas of the learners hence strive to enhance it, they further indicated that records management enable the teacher to group according to abilities hence quick learning through confidence rather than intimidation of slow learners by quick learners.

Recommendations

The study recommends that educators should look for specific learning techniques that will help to improve student achievement and content literacy. Cooperative learning methods will most

likely be one of the learning techniques teachers must embrace for exploring attempt of providing a learning environment conducive to higher student achievement.

There is also need to ensure that cooperative learning method have to track record of positive results in the classroom. Once the proper amount of background information has been attained by the teacher , an educated choice can be made as to which cooperative learning technique are best suited for their classroom and students.

The study recommends teachers to monitor the dynamics of group setting , place an emphasis on collaborations of motivation , assess the mastery of learning materials by students on a group or individual basis.

The study recommend to have assessment as daily competition , quizzes, tests and any other type of assessment to increase student performance.

The study recommended teachers to ensure that learners with difficult in communication they get information taught in class by the use of very simple vocabularies during teaching and learning process .

The study recommended the government to train teachers on skills of cooperative learning as one way of helping students to learn and also to have continuous professional development to teachers on methods of teaching and learning.

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